

SECTION OF BIOLOGICAL AND MEDICAL SCIENCES

SELECTION OF PROSTHETIC DESIGNS IN THE TREATMENT OF DYSFUNCTION OF THE TEMPOROMANDIBULAR JOINT

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Abstract

The problems of temporomandibular joint dysfunction (TMJ) and its treatment have been the cause of controversy and debate in the scientific community of dental professionals for decades. However, despite deep theoretical research, orthopedic dentists who see their patients every day invariably face seemingly simple but pressing questions regarding the diagnosis and treatment of patients with TMJ dysfunction.

Keywords: dysfunction of the temporomandibular joint, displacement of the articular disc.

In our daily work, we most often encounter patients with painless TMJ dysfunction. Such patients come to the clinic for dental prosthetics. Often, during a clinical examination, only one symptom is revealed - a click of varying intensity during movements of the lower jaw [3, 5]. The clicking sound is usually associated with disc displacement. Some researchers believe that anterior displacement of the disc (ventral disc dislocation) over time can lead to blockage, restriction of mouth opening of the lower jaw and other serious consequences. And in many clinical cases this is the rationale for treatment up to the complete reconstruction of the patient's occlusion. Displacement of the articular disc is manifested by a reciprocal click, which is associated with a change in the relationship between the head of the mandible and the disc. As you know, the disc on the head is held in place by ligaments during movements of the lower jaw. Reciprocal clicking is a symptom of ligament damage within the joint. A possible cause of anterior displacement of the articular disc and ligament damage is tension resulting from the disordinated work of the upper part of the lateral pterygoid muscle, which is attached to it. Disc displacement can occur with or without reposition at the stages of incursion movements of the lower jaw. However, often anterior disc displacement is not accompanied by a clear clinical picture of dysfunction. The correct position of the discs in relation to the heads of the lower jaw is a condition for the normal functioning of the temporomandibular joints, at the same time, in many cases, the TMJ can adapt to the incorrect location of the articular disc [3, 5].

The purpose of the study is to analyze clinical cases of patients with partial absence of teeth in the upper and lower jaws who have reciprocal clicks at the time of treatment.

Material and methods.

An examination and dental treatment was carried out on patients with partial absence of teeth and TMJ

dysfunction, manifested by painless clicks, which were identified at a dental appointment and did not bother the patients in any way. The study involved 10 people aged 34 to 47 years with partial absence of teeth in the upper and lower jaw. Of these, there were 7 (70%) women and 3 (30%) men. Criteria for inclusion of patients in the study: 1) partial absence of teeth in the upper and lower jaws, which does not require changes in the occlusion of the patient's dentition; 2) included dental defects, Kennedy class 3; 3) physiological types of occlusion; 4) clicks that are clinically detectable and do not bother the patient. Criteria for excluding patients from the study: 1) partial absence of teeth in the upper and lower jaw, requiring a change in the occlusion of the patient's dentition; 2) unilateral (Kennedy class 1) and bilateral (Kennedy class 2) end defects; 3) non-physiological types of occlusion; 4) symptoms of muscular-articular dysfunction, accompanied by pain, painful sensations, forced position of the lower jaw. For diagnostic purposes, all patients underwent a clinical examination and a "Hamburg" short examination, as a diagnostic screening test to identify dysfunctional conditions at an outpatient dental appointment. When examining the oral cavity, the dental formula was recorded, the nature of the closure of the dentition and occlusal contacts were assessed. They also noted the asymmetry of mouth opening, its pain or painlessness, the volume of opening in mm, whether intra-articular noise is detected, whether the occlusion sound is asynchronous, whether palpation of the masticatory muscles is painful, whether eccentric occlusion of the teeth is traumatic. The presence or absence of dentures in the patient's oral cavity and their compliance with clinical requirements were assessed. Compliance with clinical requirements was determined based on clinical and radiological examinations. Instrumental analysis of plaster models of jaws was carried out using an ARTEX articulator. Diagnostic models were plastered into the interframe space of the articulator to analyze functional

occlusion. Installation of the models into the articulator was carried out using a face bow according to the method recommended by the manufacturer. All patients participating in our study received fixed dentures. The follow-up period for patients included in the study was 3-4 years. After 3-4 years, for the purpose of diagnosis, a clinical study and a "Hamburg" examination were repeated in all patients.

Results. Initial situation before orthopedic treatment: patients included in the study group had unilateral defects in the dentition in 54.5% of cases, bilateral defects in 18.2%, and defects in 27.3% restored by bridges that did not meet the requirements clinical requirements. Clinically, all patients had a unilateral reciprocal click when opening and closing the mouth. Movements of the lower jaw are preserved in full, free, painless, despite the presence of a click in the joint. A deviation of the lower jaw was detected when opening the mouth, but the displacement was within 2 mm. Palpation of the masticatory muscles was painless. Primary contacts in centric relation were determined in 45.5% of cases on the first premolars, in 55.5% - on the second premolars. In habitual occlusion, uniform contacts were revealed on both sides. When studying the dynamic occlusion of the dentition, canine guidance was revealed on the right and left sides in 72.7% of the examined. Group function was observed in 27.3%. During protrusion management, 90.9% of patients had the norm - at least two central incisors in contact; in one patient - 9.1% - complete disocclusion between the incisors. At the same time, in the right, left, lateral and anterior occlusions, there were no premature contacts on the working and balancing sides in balancing and hyperbalancing. All patients included in the study received fixed dentures. During clinical examination of patients after 3-4 years, not a single patient was found to have limited mouth opening. The patients still did not complain of discomfort either in the muscles or in the temporomandibular joints. A click was detected in 10 of 11 patients. In one patient, no clicks were detected, which was apparently due to complete ventral disc dislocation without reduction. However, the patient did not make any complaints, but stated this as an improvement when asked to compare these two conditions. Fixed dentures met clinical (orthopedic) requirements after 3-4 years. Conclusion. A clinical analysis of patients with partial absence of teeth in the upper and (or) lower jaw and reciprocal clicks in the temporomandibular joint did not subsequently reveal problems with the

temporomandibular joints in the form of blocking in patients who underwent orthopedic treatment while maintaining the existing occlusal relationships lower jaw or limited mouth opening. The observation period is 3-4 years after orthopedic treatment. Based on the results of observations, it can be assumed that in those clinical situations where there are no indications for changing the occlusion (reconstruction of the occlusion, changing the occlusal scheme) and clicks do not cause inconvenience or discomfort to patients, it is possible to carry out orthopedic treatment while maintaining the patient's usual occlusion.

Conclusions. Noise in the temporomandibular joint can be considered not as a problem, but as a risk factor. Displacement of the articular disc with reposition may be asymptomatic and does not require treatment, since the joint structures can adapt to different positions of the disc [1, 5]. Some authors have proposed a distinction between the concepts of "disc displacement" and "anterior disc position." The latter term may indicate a physiological condition. However, there are still no reliable criteria by which the differences between them can be accurately diagnosed [6]. Further scientific research is necessary, since the question remains open about the need and advisability of radical intervention in cases where the dental system is in the stage of adaptation to the changes that have occurred.

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